

Kinetics and Mechanism of Anation of *cis*-Diaquobis-(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) Ion by Glycine in Acid Media

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Anation of *cis*-diaquobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) by glycine has been studied at 60° and I=0.5 mol dm⁻³. The following rate law has been established in the pH range 2.84-3.95,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_0[H^+] + k_1K_1}{[H^+]\left\{1 + \frac{K_1}{K_d}\right\} + K_1 + \frac{[H^+]^2}{K_d}}$$

The second order anation rate constants (k_0 and k_1) for the species *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ and *cis*-[Co(en)₂(OH)(H₂O)]²⁺ by glycine (gly) are found to be $2.94 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ and $13.6 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$, respectively at 60°, where K_1 and K_d are acid dissociation constants of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ and *N*-protonated glycine (gly H⁺), respectively. The spectral analysis indicates that the end-product of the reaction is probably *cis*-[(en)₂Co(H₂O)O, CCH₂NH₂]²⁺.

THE kinetics of anation of Co(NH₃)₆H₂O³⁺ by a variety of carboxylate ligands have been extensively studied¹⁻¹³. Anation of aquopentaamine cobalt(III) by glycine was first studied by Yamazaki and Saito¹⁴. Subsequently Banerjee and Roy¹⁰ have reinvestigated it and essentially supported the mechanism suggested by Yamazaki and Saito. The anation reaction is believed to proceed through the formation of reactive ion-pair between the cobalt(III) substrate and the anating anion in a rapid preequilibrium step followed by rate determining expulsion of the ligand water molecule from cobalt(III) centre by a dissociative interchange (I_d) process. However, when carboxylic acids are anating species, the reaction follows second order kinetics and the existence of the carboxylic acid-aquo cation ion-pairs as the reactive intermediates are not often observed. Not much work has been done to study anation of N₄Co(H₂O)₂³⁺ by different ligands. The anation of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ (en = ethylenediamine) by oxalate species in acidic medium has been studied by Harris *et al.*^{15,16} and Stranks and Vanderhock¹⁷. The anation of diaquobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) by ethylenediamine was studied by De and Pal¹⁸ and by benzoic acid was studied by Chaudhury and Siddhanta¹⁹.

It was considered of some interest to study the anation of *cis*-diaquobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) by glycine.

Experimental

Trans-[Co(en)₂Cl₂]Cl was prepared by the method of Krishnamurty²⁰. It was converted to [Co(en)₂CO₃]ClO₄ by treatment with Na₂CO₃, heating the mixture till a deep red solution developed

and then precipitated with NaClO₄. The crude sample was recrystallised from water. Acidification of the latter compound gave stable *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺, the uv-visible spectrum of which was in good agreement with that reported^{20,21}. Glycine, sodium perchlorate, perchloric acid were of AnalaR grade. pH measurements were made with a Elico LI 120 digital pH meter using combined electrode. Uv-visible spectra were recorded by a Varian Cary 634S recording spectrophotometer. The *cis*-[Co(en)₂(OH)₂]²⁺ was generated by acidification of the carbonate complex with standard HClO₄; CO₂ was removed by passing air. This sample was used for anation studies. A known volume of the aquo complex was transferred into the reaction flask and the volume was made up with distilled water at the reaction temperature. pH of the solution was immediately measured. The progress of the reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquots of reaction mixture at definite time intervals, cooling down to room temperature and then measuring optical density with a Varian Cary 634S recording spectrophotometer at 495 nm. The observed pseudo-first order rate constants for anation reaction were obtained from the slope of the linear plot of (A_∞ - A_t) vs time, where A_t and A_∞ stand for O.D. of the reaction mixture at time *t* and for the complete anation of the diaquo complex under the condition, respectively.

Determination of stoichiometry of the reaction :

To determine stoichiometry of the reaction, 0.1 mol dm⁻³ glycine (5 ml) was titrated potentiometrically against 0.091 mol dm⁻³ NaOH in presence of CH₂O (Fig. 1b) 0.1 mol dm⁻³ glycine (5 ml) was shaken well with Dowex 50W-X8 cation-exchanger in H⁺-form and the washings with distilled water was treated with CH₂O maintained at pH 7; the result-

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration of glycine: (a) $[\text{gly}]_T = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (b) $[\text{gly}]_T = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ after subjecting to ion-exchange with Dowex 50W-X8 resin, and (c) reaction mixture after completion of anation with Dowex 50W-X8 resin in H^+ -form and ion-exchange separation of the cobalt(III) species $[\text{gly}]_T = 0.1$, $[\text{diaquo}]_T = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; for all titrations $0.091 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaOH was used as the titrant.

ing solution was potentiometrically titrated against $0.091 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaOH (Fig. 1a). 5 ml of the reaction mixture after completion of the reaction

was allowed to be exchanged with Dowex 50W-X8 cation-exchanger in H^+ -form so that the complex formed is retained in the resin bed and unreacted glycine got liberated; the resin washings along with the filtrate was treated with CH_2O maintained at pH 7 and the resulting solution potentiometrically titrated against $0.091 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaOH (Fig. 1c). From the end-point of different titrations the amount of glycine bound to Co^{III} was determined and hence stoichiometry of the reaction could be determined. It was observed that one mole of glycine reacted with one mole of *cis*-diaquo bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III).

Results and Discussion

(i) The kinetic results can be summarised as follows:

Pseudo-first order rate constants were determined at various $[\text{glycine}]_T$ and at constant pH 2.93. The plot of k_{obs} against $[\text{glycine}]_T$ in the range $0.03 < [\text{gly}]_T \leq 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was linear (Fig. 2) passing through origin. A small deviation from linearity was, however, evident at $[\text{gly}]_T > 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. This may be due to the ion-pairing of the aquo-complex by glycine. k_{obs} increases with increase of pH of the solution at a fixed $[\text{gly}]_T$. For example, at $[\text{diaquo}]_T = 0.005$, $[\text{gly}]_T = 0.1$ and $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ increases from 1.54 to 5.22 when pH of the reaction mixture was increased from 2.84 to 3.95 (Table 1). Hence, a more reactive species is generated with increase of pH. The hydroxo-aquo-complex *cis*- $[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ is

Fig. 2. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{gly}]_T$ at pH=2.93, temp=60° and $I=0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING pH ON ANATION OF CIS-DIAQUOBIS(ETHYLENEDIAMINE)COBALT(III) BY GLYCINATE

$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$	5.22	4.99	3.61	2.94	2.27	1.88	1.81	1.54
pH	3.95	3.93	3.63	3.47	3.22	3.03	2.93	2.84

considered to be the reacting cobalt(III) substrate along with the diaquo-complex. The tentative mechanism of anation is suggested as Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Under pseudo-first order condition of $[\text{gly}]_{\text{T}}$, the rate law is given by equation (1),

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_0[\text{H}^+] + k_1 K_1}{[\text{H}^+] \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_1}{K_d} \right\} + K_1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_d}} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) can be linearised to equation (2),

$$k_{\text{obs}} \left\{ [\text{H}^+] \left(1 + \frac{K_1}{K_d} \right) + K_1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_d} \right\} = k_0[\text{H}^+] + k_1 K_1 \quad (2)$$

pK_a of glycine at 60° is taken²¹ to be 2.35. pK_{a1} of *cis*-diaquocomplex at 25° (6.1 ; $I=1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)²² was temperature corrected using the calculated ΔH values for the acid dissociation equilibrium of *cis*-[(trien)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺; the values of K_1 at 60° turned out to be $7.04 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The reactivity ratio ($k_1/k_0=469$) reflects strong *cis*-labilising action of the hydroxo group of *cis*-[(en)₂Co(OH)(H₂O)]²⁺, since the values of the equilibrium constants of the precursor ion-pairs of the diaquo- and aquo-hydroxo cations with $\text{NH}_2^+\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2^-$ are likely to be comparable. The plot of $k_{\text{obs}} \left\{ [\text{H}^+] \left(1 + \frac{K_1}{K_d} \right) + K_1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_d} \right\}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ was found

to be linear (Fig. 3) supporting the proposed mechanism. The values of k_0 and k_1 were found to be $2.94 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ and $13.6 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$, respectively. The proposed Scheme of anation of *cis*-diaquobis(ethylenediamine) by glycinate suggest that the hydroxoquo-complex react with a much faster rate than the diaquo-complex. The apparent activation parameters, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$, calculated from temperature dependence of k_{obs} at pH 3, were found to be $146.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $167.4 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively.

Nature of the product: Fig. 4 presents the spectral changes of the reaction mixtures during

 Fig. 3. Plot of $k_{\text{obs}} \left\{ [\text{H}^+] \left(1 + \frac{K_1}{K_d} \right) + K_1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_d} \right\}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$.

 Fig. 4. Successive spectral scan during the anation of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(OH₂)₂]³⁺ by glycine; $[\text{diaquo}]_{\text{T}}=5.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $[\text{gly}]_{\text{T}}=0.1$, $I=0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH=3.1, temp.=55°; reaction quenched by cooling and spectrum taken at room temperature: (a) aquo-complex alone; (b) - (f) for the mixture (b) 15 (c) 60 (d) 120 (e) 180 (f) 720 min.

the course of anation. The final spectrum exhibits $\lambda_{\max}$ at 495 and 358 nm with $\epsilon = 103.8$ and $80.4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The chelated glycinato-complex $\text{cis}[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2)]^{2+}$ is reported by Alexander and Busch²³ to display $\lambda_{\max}$ at 487 and 346 nm with $\epsilon = 98$ and $107 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively which also agree well with our earlier findings²⁴ ($488 (98 \pm 2)$, $347(105)$). This leads us to believe that the chelated glycinato-complex is not the reaction product. Since the glycine in the pH range studied, exists in the betaine form ($\text{N}^+\text{H}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2^-$), it is most likely that anation site is the carboxylate end and the product is $\text{cis}[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_3)]^{2+}$.

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